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Transcript

Speaker 1

Hello. Hi. Hi, I would like to thank you for taking your time to participate in this research.

Speaker 2

You're welcome.

Speaker 1

My name is Anna Makarudze. I'm a master student at Bleeding and Institute of Technology. I'm studying a master's in social engineering and I'm conducting research to investigate how developers perceive vulnerabilities in open source dependencies, which they rely on in their projects. And for a study, just some ethical issues, participation in this research is entirely for that, and you can withdraw at any time. You can choose to skip some questions that you're not comfortable answering and we will not retain any personal data or identifiable information. I will not share your name, role, or e-mail address with anyone who will observe GDPR rules, and your responses will remain anonymous and not links to your project. And this recording will only be shared with my supervisors in Dixia Manor for the sake of verifying the data collection process. And it will be deleted as soon as the master is done. So. So before we start, could you please introduce yourself? OK, so my research is focused on five programming languages or ecosystems, Python, Java, Ruby, PHP, JavaScript. And I'll be also focusing on five web frameworks, one from each of these ones, Django, Spring Boot, Ruby on Rails, Next.js, and Laravel.

So before you start, maybe would you introduce yourself and tell me which ecosystem you're coming from, and also whether you're a developer just using a black web framework, or are you a contributor or a maintainer? And also, how many years of experience do you have in software development?

Speaker 2

OK, so I'm a Java developer. I have been working in industry for over 7 years as a core Java developer. Right now I'm doing my masters, but about till about one year back, I was a developer associated with the industry.

And mostly you can say that my seven years of experience that I have, I was a developer in the banking domain. So I have knowledge using Core Java and Spring Boot framework, and also I develop microservices extensively using these technologies.

Speaker 1

All right, thank you. Do you by any chance contribute to any open source projects or for now you just use them in your project?

Speaker 2

I would say in the time when I was part of the industry, there was no open source project that I was contributing to. And since it was a banking domain, we were also very, we ensured like security was our top most importance there.

So no open source projects were being used by us. But once I am, now that I'm doing my masters, there has been a few based on the course projects that I'm studying on. I have, let's say, contributed to some there.

Speaker 1

All right. Thank you. Okay, so I wanted to know when you're working with Spring Boot, do you use any other packages from other ecosystems, say JavaScript or Python, or do you just use it by yourself?

Speaker 2

Not exactly. When I'm using Spring Boot, I do use the dependencies. I use Maven dependencies, Spring Boot Maven dependencies. And we don't really use any other ecosystem packages because, for example, When we are developing a project using Java and Springboard, we also have to write JUnit test cases.

And you can set any other dependencies that we might use, that would be some JUnit related dependencies. And I was mostly a backend developer, so I might, the dependencies that I handled, they were focused on Java and Spring Boot primarily.

Speaker 1

All right. You mentioned that you worked in the banking industry and security as a top priority. Would you explain to me how security issues were reported in the end and managed within your project?

Speaker 2

So we developed our projects in sprints and our sprints would have a span of around 2 weeks. So what happened was after every four sprints, we would have some tasks in our backlog that would deal with checking for our packages that we are using and if they are the latest version.

And also we had an enterprise tool that we used to detect whether any vulnerabilities were detected in those tools. So we did this cyclically after every four sprints without fail. So we took in tasks that were primarily focused on removing vulnerabilities from dependencies and upgrading those dependency versions.

So this was something which was given a lot of importance. And during that time, I remember that we would not be taking any requirements from the customers. All our development work would be put on hold, and every member of the team would be focused on removing these vulnerabilities and upgrading the versions. And that included spring versions as well.

Speaker 1

Thank you for that. OK, next question I want to ask you, how conscious are you of the dangers that are vulnerable, vulnerable dependencies present to your project?

Speaker 2

OK, so honestly speaking, we were not very conscious about that when we were coding for it because we knew that there would be a time coming at the end of, let's say, 4 sprints where we would be focused on fixing our vulnerability errors coming from the packages.

So in that way, we knew that we would be given some time to address those issues. So always, since ours was a fast-paced development project, we would focus on just getting the features ready in time. And then during our allotted time, we would be focused on looking for vulnerabilities. But during our development coding, we never really gave that much thought, to be honest.

Speaker 1

All right, thank you. And then how are your supply chain attacks and their effects on projects, especially with the pressures to dependencies within your dependency tree?

Speaker 2

I would say I'm not very aware of this. Again, since I was a backend developer, my work was mostly focused on getting the features ready. And then if any securities as such came up,

we knew that we would again all jump in and put some quick fix to just make sure it was not affecting anything.

I do remember a particular instance, I think this was the year 2021, and there was this whole Log4j issue that had come out, the security error. And I remember during that time, our entire team, we used to use a lot of Log4j dependencies across our code base.

So we spent like a week and even over time trying to get rid of all the Log4j dependencies that we were using. So again, it was as a need basis that we were very focused on the catering for security-related errors.

We only addressed them when they cropped up. So this was a Log4j issue I clearly remember because we spent like even the weekend trying to roll back our changes where we had made use of the Log4j dependency.

And also it was not easy because once we removed that, a lot of, we had to also refactor the code accordingly across different places. So that showed that when we were actually using the Log4j, we were not very cautious when we were using it.

Speaker 1

Okay, thank you. And what tools did you use to identify vulnerable depends within your project.

Speaker 2

I remember we used Sonar Cloud where sometimes dependency vulnerabilities would show up there. And apart from that, we had an enterprise approved tool, internal tool, that would help us detect those dependency issues as well is, for example, versioning errors, it will show you what was the latest version that we we must be using that is devoid of any vulnerabilities. Yeah.

Speaker 1

And what what factors influenced you to update to newer versions of the dependencies within your projects? Did you stick to whatever dependencies that we're using, or do you apply regularly or do you wait until maybe there's a security advisory for you to update to new dependencies?

Speaker 2

No, we did this upgrading our versions. We did it every three months. So it was without fail, even if no vulnerabilities were there, we would have like specific times allotted to upgrade our package versions every three months.

Speaker 1

And then sometimes with open source dependencies, they might not get maintained for a long time. Maybe the creator moved on due to many other reasons. So I want to understand how would you check the maintenance of dependencies in your project?

Would you know whether a dependence is no longer being maintained, but you kept using it for you keep track to see which ones are becoming deprecated, and then you try.

Speaker 2

To, because our code base was so big and we have legacy code and also new code, we were very scared of touching the code base, so we wouldn't really remove anything. So you would say that the dependencies would stay there even if we can see that they're deprecated.

And maybe let's say once a year, if we were feeling brave enough, we would attempt to maybe solve that, but then solve the deprecation issues by upgrading some packages. But I also remember one instance when we had this one venture in a year where we were going go for gold for all the code bases.

where everything needs to be perfect. And we started working on that and it broke a lot of flows. And so we immediately abandoned that idea and was like, no, let's keep it.

And this mostly we noticed in the legacy code.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And then suppose you have a dependency in the legacy code. That is, that is vulnerabilities, then would you still leave it in the legacy code or would you, how would you handle that?

Speaker 2

No, that would be a very challenging because then it's just not a quick fix. Then it would be like, it would involve discussion with a lot of stakeholders, like how do we get handle this? And then there would be workshops done and several meetings. And then maybe we would, if it was blocking anything or it was extremely urgent, then only then it would be picked up. Otherwise not. Otherwise we just will, okay, leave it until maybe a defect comes up. But if it was for sure it would cause an issue in production, then we would definitely have to address it. But except for that, we would just leave it there. Again, I was in the banking domain, and it was very important that business was going on as usual. There can't be any interruptions.

Speaker 1

All right. And then how long would it take you to say updated vulnerable dependence? I know you mentioned that you would work on them maybe after some sprints how long would that take? No money. After you cover that.

Speaker 2

It would take, let's say, around 5-6 people would be assigned to take care of this, and each person would probably take a week's time to fix it if there were some issues found.

Otherwise, it was a fairly quick upgrade, changing of dependence, I mean, upgrading the dependencies.

It was not that difficult if there were no underlying issues or any flows being broken. So that would, if everything was going well, it would take maybe 2 days. And then after that, we would do thorough testing of all our flows, unit tests to see none of the flows were breaking. But then, On an average, I would say it would have taken one week per person.

Speaker 1

Thank you. Okay. So, if any of the projects that you went to have ever been exposed to supply chain attacks?

Speaker 2

Could you give me some example of supply chain attacks?

Speaker 1

Okay, for example, recently, in November 2025, there was a supply chain attack that affected users using Gainsight applications when they updated it caused malicious actors to access data from Salesforce through an updating of independence that caused like one attack with Gainsight. It's an attack on Salesforce account that was extracted for about 200 companies, so that would be like an example. So, with the supply chain attack one, attack on one organization can lead to attacks on other organizations that are using your APIs or using your dependencies, so it's kind of like cascade throughout, so...Do you have a similar experience where an attack on either one of your organizations that you were extended to you or maybe an attack from you extended to others?

Speaker 2

No, unfortunately, I never encountered that, at least during my tenure as a developer. Yeah.

Speaker 1

Thank you.

Speaker 1

And then what factors help you to address vulnerable dependencies within your projects?

O2 maybe?

Speaker 2

OK, yeah. So we had, like I mentioned, we had some dedicated internal tools, enterprise tools that would detect the vulnerabilities and it would come up as either severe or medium or not so severe level, it would be given those, what do you call that, markers.

Yeah, exactly. And then based on severity, we would address them. And also, SonarCloud sometimes also showed up, showed the vulnerabilities and we ensured that we didn't have any severe vulnerabilities. So these enterprise tools combined with Sonar Cloud, they helped us to fix the vulnerability issues.

Speaker 1

Alright, thank you. And what challenges would hinder you from addressing vulnerable dependencies in your project?

Speaker 2

So yes, so mostly when we would upgrade, change our dependencies or upgrade to a newer version, we would see a part of the flow is breaking. And also in Java, certain packages were dependent on the versions of an other packages. So if we change the version of 1 package, then it would, the other package would become incompatible and then it would require us to change the versions of the other dependent packages as well.

So this was something that works negatively towards our, what do you say, our interest to upgrade versions because we know if it's not about changing just one version of a package, it means all the other dependent packages also get changed. And that sometimes may lead to changing some, making some modifications in code.

And not always do we have the bandwidth to do that during in the industry. So yeah, that is, this is 1 factor that kind of deters us from being open to upgrading.

Speaker 1

Okay, thank you. And do you have any recommendations for dependence management

Speaker 2

Yes, one that I can think of is when for every dependency, at least if there was a way to know that what are the other dependencies linked to one particular dependency, then it makes developers informed, make them do informed choices that, okay, if I need to upgrade one version of a package, then what can be the potential other packages I need to change as well? and then change my code accordingly, because developers spend a lot of time investigating what other dependencies might get affected, and that takes up their time. So if we know that during some change of dependency, what can be the impact or underlying changes, then it helps greatly.

Speaker 1

Thank you. That's very useful. I think we have managed to answer all of the questions that I have. Some of your answers covered the questions that I didn't ask, so I'll skip them.

Speaker 2

Oh, great.

Speaker 1

Thank you so much for taking your time to participate in the interview.

Speaker 2

Thank you.

Speaker 1

I will stop recording now.